

Eliminate the Shadow: IT Solutions to Secure the Looming Threat of the Internet of Things

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is changing the world with a range of smart connected devices. The downside is that this interconnectedness creates a large number of serious security flaws. Summary: A review of the IoT security threats and the current solutions adopted to counter them, a critique of such solutions. Aside from finding that there is no one solution that fully solves these challenges, the review underscores the importance of a multi-faceted approach that entails secure coding, lightweight cryptography, firmware updates, network segregation, and industry-wide standardization. Finally, it highlights important knowledge gaps will leaves to be filled by future investigation to develop the Trust in the IoT ecosystem.

Introduction

The recent rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) in the last 3-4 years, is more than just a story. The IoT boasts a future in which everything from home appliances to cars to industrial sensors are able to quickly and easily connect to the internet. Yet, with vast interconnectivity comes vast opportunity for malicious actors to attack. Moreover, this is particularly dangerous for many IoT devices (e.g., those with limited processing power and memory) given their resource-constrained nature (Makris et al., 2020). The problem is made worse by weak authentication protocols and insecure firmware too (Rad, 2019). Depending on the context, these vulnerabilities can be exploited for everything, from data thefts and privacy violations or to the disruption of a critical infrastructure to actually causing physical harm.

This survey is targeted to identify the challenges in terms of security for the IoT. It shows the distinct security threats, current methods for mitigating these threats and evaluates them in the other sections. This review characterizes the strength of current solutions and limitations and helps to identify what areas need further research to bring about more secure and reliable IoT environment.

Security Threats in the IoT

The IoT landscape is heavily punished by a number of significant security threats. Some of them are:

Weak Authentication:

The ability of an attacker to use weak authentication protocols or weaknesses in device firmware to connect to an IoT device or exploit the network it is part of (Haitjema et al., 2019). This could in turn enable them to steal sensitive data, sabotage operations or even hijack the device to conduct other cyberattacks.

Data Breaches:

With IoT devices gathering and sending a multitude of information, from user locational data to habits and, in the case of wearables, even sensitive (health and other) personal information, the use of insecure devices may lead to data leaks (Abu-Taineh et al., 2018).

Botnets:

Essentially, malware can be installed on a compromised IoT device manufacturing a vulnerability which then can be a part of a botnet - a network of devices which are individually controlled by an attacker to launch DoS attacks or spread malware (Chen et al., 2017). These types of attacks may disrupt essential infrastructure and online services.

Direct Physical Damage:

In critical infrastructure applications, the implications of a successful attack that gains unauthorized control of devices that control physical security and infrastructure systems (utility systems like power grids and water/wastewater distribution as well as industrial control systems) can be catastrophic and pose a threat to life and property (Romero et al., 2018).

Attacks like those described above relies on the fact that manufacturers are not doing proper security in their IoT devices that's harmonizes the need for an enhanced security solution for IoT.

Ways to Combat IoT Security Threats

The increasing security risks of the so-called Internet of Things (IoT) has lead to several approaches being developed:

Secure Coding Practices:

Secure coding practices should be important to every phase of device development. Secure systems should include the use of strong encryption algorithms and authentication mechanism and regular vulnerability assessment (Rad,2019) But writing secure code requires skilled developers and regular security audits, both of which aren't cheap for cheap IoT devices.

Lightweight Cryptography:

Lightweight cryptographic algorithms are developed specifically for resource-constrained IoT devices, which improve security without affecting the performance (Maselli et al., 2019). Promising as the new immutable cryptographic primitives may be, light-weight cryptography is not a solved problem with a number of trade-offs between security strength and resource reality yet to be figured out as well.

Firmware Upgrades/Patching:

There must be a reliable system of updating firmware and system patching for known vulnerabilities (Haitjema et al., 2019). The trouble is that updating all diverse and widespread IoT devices must be done very often, maintaining a consistent update stream - this is a large logistics issue. Older devices also may not be designed to receive updates.

Network Segmentation:

Network segmentation stuff: Separation of the IoT devices from mission-critical operations through network segmentation which can help contain the harm caused from a compromised device (Makris et al., 2020). While network segmentation works, it can be cumbersome to implement and manage at scale.

Regulations and Standardization:

Finally, industry standards and regulations as legal principles to enforce secure IoT development and deployment are essential to maintain general safety and to encourage the industry to take responsibility (Abu-Taineh et al., 2018). However, achieving standardized security practices for such a diverse IoT industry is a challenge as enforcement mechanisms may not be easy to implement.

Analyzing the Problem with Current Solutions

This is not to say that steps haven't been taken to curb IoT security threats - there have been many - but the perfect solution is a long way off. A useful critical analysis of modern approaches:

No Single Silver Bullet:

There is no silver bullet with IoT security. Every solution has its own pros and cons. Secure coding practices are important, but can be costly for low-margin devices. While LWC looks to provide some hope in this direction, the problem in balancing security with the resource constraints on these systems still seems to be a challenge.

Logistical Hurdles:

Managing firmware updates, and patches in a uniform manner across the diverse and geographically scattered IoT devices is a tall logistical order. In addition, large numbers of older devices may be beyond their update cycle and incapable of receiving other updates, there by permanently vulnerable.

Complexity of Implementation:

But for large-scale deployments, network segmentation is very effective, however, it is also complex and resource-intensive to implement and manage.

Common Challenges in Standardization:

The diverse IoT industry continues rapidly to evolve, and developing and enforcing standardized security practices is tricky. Moreover, adhering to these standards is challenging because the IoT world is decentralized.

Finding the Most Dynamic Solution

This is essential as no single remedy is sufficient on its own to protecting IoT. This strategy could - hopefully - include:

Secure Coding Practices, Prioritized:

Including security principles in every step of the development lifecycle is still a basic necessity of the secure hardware lifecycle for IoT.

Some of the investments that are paying off:

Lightweight Cryptography : The concept of the lightweight cryptography is not new, but the remodelling it for IoT era with the goal to keep the crypto-algorithms small, fast, energy efficient and platform agnostic has invigorated researchers to solve for the IoT devices.

Further research and development in lightweight cryptography are required to strike a guardian to manage the strength of security with the computational and memory constraints of an IoT device.

Enforcing Regular Patching:

They also discuss the importance of standardized update mechanisms and robust patching protocols in order to quickly address security concerns across the whole IoT ecosystem.

Network Segmentation:

How it Works

As a best practice network segmentation is still an important tool to help reduce the impact of potentially compromised devices, especially in critical infrastructure deployments.

Encouraging Standardization and Proper Legislation

Turning to high-mindedness, we absolutely need industry collaboration and government regulation serving as the foundation for minimum security hygiene and ensuring accountability among manufacturers.

Future Research Directions and Knowledge Gaps

There has been progress, but the security of IoT continues to have several large gaps in its understanding. Areas for further research include:

Standard Security Protocols:

Ensuring these can interwork and be able to be adopted in marketplace at large requires the development of standardized security protocols that can be economically implemented given the resources.

Framework for Secure Device Management:

Secure, scalable device management frameworks - critical for simplifying patching and vulnerability management - must be able to support heterogenous IoT deployments.

Robust communication protocols:

Improve security at the protocol level, to avoid the communication protocols being tampered and hijacked.

User Education and Awareness:

This comes back to user education, which can help reduce these kinds of attacks by helping users configure IoT devices securely. User awareness of security best practices are what help mitigate human error and for that matter, social engineering attacks.

Conclusion

The success of the IoT depends on strong security implementations as well. A multipronged approach that focuses on secure coding, lightweight cryptography, patching, network segmentation, and industry-wide standards is required. Manufacturers, researchers, policymakers, and users must work together to build a secure and trusted IoT ecosystem. Additional research is required to fill gaps in knowledge already identified, and to discover new strategies to improve the security of the constantly-growing Internet of Things.

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